

The detection of Tau Biomarker using Cloning and Western blotting

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Abstract

Protein tau as a biomarker in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) are hallmarks of Alzheimer disease (AD). Several methods have been established by scientists to identify the expression of phosphorylated and total tau in patient's sample such as using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) followed by Western blotting and Mass spectrometry (MS). Recombinant tau protein is widely used technique to study cellular and pathological aspects of tauopathies. In this study, we show the expression of tau protein by cloning tau transcript variant 2 in pet29b plasmid followed by SDS-PAGE and Western blotting. We evaluated the advantages of cloning and PET system to express tau protein and we express the straightforward process to detect tau protein through cloning followed by western blotting.

Keywords: Tau, Cloning, Western Blotting, Biomarker, .

Introduction

Tau biomarker is a pivotal hallmark of Alzheimer disease. The Tau protein was detected in 1975 as essential proteins for microtubule assembly [1]. Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease has been associated with tau hyperphosphorylation which forms insoluble aggregated named neurofibrillary tangle [2]. Abnormal Tau phosphorylation results in formation of paired-helical-filament (PHF) and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs) [3].

The access of total tau level in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) which is the result of neurodegeneration is a key characteristic of Alzheimer disease however, it has been detected at early stage of disease when neurodegeneration is partial and can be normal at progressive stage [4].

However, CSF sampling include invasive and unpleasant lumbar punctures procedure which encourage scientist to investigate blood-based tau biomarkers among patients and controls. The studies show plasma/serum p-tau181, p-tau217, and t-tau were shown to be elevated in AD compared with control group [5].

Moreover, mass spectrometry in human saliva revealed that salivary tau species can be replaced with CSF in measuring the level of t-tau biomarker for AD diagnosis specially at early stage [6]. Although CSF is not an ideal sample source for screening of AD disease, it is still more reliable diagnostic approach for AD

patients, as the tau protein is beta 3 transferrin which present in CSF but not found in blood, nasal secretion or other body fluid [7]. Different approaches are used to detect tau protein in AD disease. Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging, Innotest enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) in CSF are common method used to investigate tau protein [8]. However, cloning and western blotting in investigation of tau but not in clinical use, is preferential methods due to some of the advantages which other methods lack including isolation of a DNA sequence, simplicity, cost effectiveness, rapidity and reliability of cloning [9]. Furthermore, the advantages of western blots involve the detection of protein in picogram levels as well as being as effective early diagnostic tools [10].

Material and Methods

1. Cloning of tau transcript variant 2 into pet29b plasmid

A tau/pet29b (addgene,Cambridge, MA, USA) were constructed for the rocominant expression of tau transcript variant 2. The cloning method is restriction enzyme The coding sequence of tau restriction variant2 was generated by PCR (table 1) and cloned between 5' cloning site NdeI and 3' cloning site EcoRI of the pet29b (addgene, UK) containing kanamycin-resistance and lacI-encoding genes (Figure 1). Exprestion was initiated with the addition of isopropyl β-D-1 thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG).

Figure1: the tau/pet29b expression plasmid used in this study A schematic representation of the pet29b plasmid into which tau transcript variant 2 construct was cloned. The NdeI and EcoRI restrictin sites between which tau was cloned are shown, as ell as the genes encoding the LacI repressor (lacI), kanamycin resistance (KanR) and origin of replication (f1 ori) and (ori).

Primer	Sequence (5' to 3')
Sequencing(Forward)	TCACTTTAGTTGCCCTTCCCCC
Sequencing(Reverse)	CCGCACATGGCACCGTAAAG

Table1 : DNA sequencing primers.

2. Transformation of competent cells

4 nanograms of plasmid DNA was added to 50 µl competent BL21

DE3 and incubated on ice for 30 min. Cells were heat shocked at 42° C for 70 s, followed by 2 min incubation on ice. 1000 µl LB broth was added and the mixture incubated at 37° C for 1 h. 50 µl of the mixture was plated on LB agar supplemented with kanamycin (100 µg/ml) and chloramphenicol (40 µg/ml) and incubated at 37° C.

3. Expresstion of the tau transcript variant 2 constructs

Single colonies were incubated into 10 ml LB broth and incubated overnight at 37°C. the day after , 1ml of the overnight culture was incubated into 50ml LB broth and grown at 37°C with 170 rpm agitation. Cultures were grown until reaching OD600=0.6-0.7 , negative IPTG 1ml in fridge , positive IPTG 500 µl incubate 3-4 hours. 1.5 ml aliquots were centrifuged at ~10,000Xg for 1 min. The pellet resuspended in 100 µl phosphate buffered saline (PBS) and re-centrifuged at ~10,000Xg for 5 min. The supernatant fraction were pipetted into Eppendorf tube for gel electrophoresis. The pellet was resuspended in 500 µl PBS and centrifuged (~10,000Xg for 5 min). Tau expression in the negative IPTG and Positive IPTG were analysed by sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) and Western blotting (WB) as described below.

4. SDS-PAGE and WB

Protein samples were separated on standard 15% Tris-glycine SDS-PAGE with (running gels and stacking gels) β-mercaptoethanol and 5 min heating at 95° C.sample ere prepared with 50 µg total protein in 4X sample buffer (20% glycerol, 0.01% promophenol blue, 0.08% SDS), incubated for 7 minutes at RT before being loaded onto the gel. sample were analyzed against a protein ladder (PageRuler plus prestained Pritein Ladder, ThermoFisher, UK, size range 10-250 kDa) for 35 min at 200 V Biorad mini-PROTEAN Tetra system (BioRad Laboratories, California, USA) and stained with Instant Blue (Coomassie-based stained from BioRa Laboratories, California,USA) for 1 h at room temperature (RT) with 3 washing steps and imaged using a SynGene G-Box imaging system. To identify tau-positive bands, WB was performed prior to antibody detection as described below.

Gels were transferred on to Amersham Hybond electrochemiluminescence nitrocellulose membrane (GE Healthcare,UK) and blocked for 15 min an then incubate with primary antibody (1:5000 dilution, polyclonal rabbit anti-human tau A0024, Thermo Fisher,UK) overnight at 4° C. It washed to remove unbounded antibody 3 times 5 mins with 10% TBS-Tween prior incubation at RT for 1 h with secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit IgG 31460, Thermo Fisher,UK, 1:5000 dilution) and the membrane washed as previously. Antibody detection was performed using Amersham ECL Prime detection reagent and visualized by exposure to X-ray film (FUJI DI-HL) and developed in White Mountain Imaging's T2 RP (White Mountain Imaging, Webster,

Result

Tau/pet29b plasmids encoding tau transcript variant 2 were created. The coding sequence were generated by PCR from templet and cloned into the NdeI and EcoRI of the pet29b as described. The plasmid description is available in figure1. Moreover, each plasmid had a cleavable N-terminal 6xHis tag for purification by immobilized metal affinity chromatography which we did not purified protatin at this experiment.

The SDS-PAGE were used to detect IPTG positive and negative templet after IPTG induction. The IPTG positive were approximately 44 KDa (figure2).

Figure2: Tau/pet29b patients sample after induction by IPTG show 45KDa size. The control sample induced by IPTG also show 45KDa.

Tau-positive fractions, identified after SDS-PAGE and Western blotting. After IPTG induction, The control sample and patient samples were analyzed by Western blotting using the A0024 antitau antibody Figure 3.

Figure3: The pathogenic sample of tau/pet29b after incubation with antitau antibody. The control sample does not contain the full-length Tau , whereas pathogenic samples show the expression of tau in almost 50KDa

Discussion

75% of the 35.6 million dementia cases worldwide are diagnosed with the most common neurodegenerative disease, Alzheimer's disease (AD) and it is expected to double by 2030 and triple by 2050 [11]. They hyperphosphorylation of tau and formation of

neurofibrillary tangle (NFT) are the pathological hallmarks of AD [12]. High level of phosphorylated tau (p-tau) and total tau (t-tau) in cerebrospinal fluid are these pathological changes [13].

Human tau is encoded by the microtubule -associated protein tau gene located on chromosome 17q21 [14].Tau present six isoforms due to alternative splicing of the MAPT gene. Isoform 2 is the longest and the most common used in tau studies with molecular mass of 45.850 KDa [15]. This variant (2) lacks three internal coding exons, as compared to variant 6. The reading frame is not affected and the resulting isoform (2) has identical N- and C-termini but lacks three segments, as compared to isoform 6 [15].

From methodological perspective, different approaches has been proposed to detect tau protein in AD sample of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) and brain tissue . a recent study the separation of CSF protein using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) followed by Western blotting incubated in tau antibodies binding to different tau domains sho wing the most abundant variants in CSF [16]. The other commonly used technique is Mass spectrometry (MS) to characterize tau variants. However, different approaches needs to be undertaken to bring up the sensitivity of CSF to detect tau and its variants, as CSF is a complex matrix [17].

Having said that studying specifical transcript variant 2 , as it is the longest and the most common isoform in AD CSF sample with cloning is the approach we have taken as cloning is more reliable and reproducibile and PET system is the most powerful system yet developed for the cloning and expression of recombinant proteins in E.coli. Target genes are cloned in pET plasmids under control of strong bacteriophage T7 RNA polymerase in the host cell. T7 RNA polymerase is so selective and active that almost all of the cell's resources are converted to target expression. The desired product can produce more than 50% of the total cell protein a few hours after induction [18]. Another important benefit of the system is its ability to maintain target genes transcriptionally silent in the uninduced state. Targent genes are initially cloned using hosts that do not contain the T7 RNA polymerase gene, thus eliminating plasmid instability due to the production of proteins potentially toxic to the host cell. Once established in a non-copy of the T7 RNA polymerase gene under lacUV5 control, and expression is induced by the addition of IPTG [18].

The Present polyclonal anti-Tau antibody was produced by immunizing animals with N-terminal of Tau and can detect approx 45-70 kDa and 100-kDa bands in brain tissues. In our study the CSF of AD patient was taken from National Hospital for Neurology and Neurosurgery (UCL) . As the result indicates the Western blotting under incubation of tau antibody andfter induction by IPTC showing that our patient sample had 45 KDa bands of tau protein whereas control sample did not present any band.

Conclusion

Having investigated the affected parameters of the production of recombinant tau protein, our current experiments detect the 45 kDa band of tau transcript variant 2 in Western blotting of AD sample whereas no band was detected in control sample. As such, this report demonstrates efficient methods for the production of tau protein as a biomarker that can be used in tauopathies studied.

Consent for Publication

Not applicable

Availability of Data and Material

The data used and analyzed in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Contributors

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